

Impact of atmospheric boundary layer profiling

Chapter: Satellite applications

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Authors	Main author: <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Anca Nemuc, INOE, National Institute for R&D for Optoelectronics, Romania Other contributors: <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Lukas Pfitzenmaier, Institute of Geophysics and Meteorology, University of Cologne, Germany• Ewan O'Connor, Finnish Meteorological Institute, Finland

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1 Introduction

Well-established programs for satellites are dedicated to ABL (Atmospheric Boundary Layer) profiling measurements but these data needs calibration/validation from the ground and here is where PROBE's network plays a very important role. High-resolution profile validation of aerosol, cloud, and precipitation is challenging, therefore best practice protocols for validation of these products have been proposed lately in the scientific community and several campaigns have been planned and some of them implemented already. This chapter contains information on satellite calibration/validation campaigns, ESA-European Space Agency (www.esa.int), EUMETSAT (<https://www.eumetsat.int/about-eumetsat>)- and NASA (www.nasa.gov) projects/missions in close connections with PROBE's instruments and products but also references to some articles involving PROBE's products and satellite data.

2 FRM4RADAR

FRM4RADAR-94 GHz Miniature Network for EarthCARE Reference Measurements is an ESA-funded project that aims to establish an observation network for validation, verification and calibration of EarthCARE-Earth Cloud, Aerosol and Radiation Explorer), a joint European/Japanese (ESA / JAXA / NICT) satellite, the sixth of ESA's Earth Explorer Programme. The 94 GHz Miniature Network provides cloud profile measurements using ground-based, high-quality remote sensing observations. FRM4RADAR has acquired, deployed, operated and exploited cloud radars at two new sites (Sweden, Romania), extending by this the geographical coverage of cloud observations in Europe towards North and East. The project is carried out by PROBE partners at the University of Cologne (lead) supported by INOE, FMI and SMHI. PROBE has facilitated the project realisation through joint workshops and knowledge transfer, especially in WG4. The project has defined operation procedures and data handling procedures and led to the development of specific tools and products to be applied for EarthCARE Cal/Val activities after the planned launch in May 2024. Within a current extension, a simulator is applied to the ground-based radars in order to make possible a 1:1 comparison of the level1. In addition, FRM4Radar developed a forward operator transforming ground-based radar

measurements into EarthCARE CPR view- see Figure 1 (reflectivity) data.

Figure 1: a) show the ground based Ze measurements of the INOE operated 94-GHz radar, and c) the simulated satellite CPR ZeECnoise (noise included). In b) the histogram of the ground based reactivities is plotted. In d) also the histogram of the satellite view is plotted. Shown are data from 22 January 2021.

All measurements of the FRM4Radar project are presented in the Quick-look Browser of the project (<https://geomet.uni-koeln.de/forschung/frm4radar/quicklooks>).

3 Sentinel 5p/ TROPOMI Validation

On 13 October 2017 the Copernicus Sentinel 5 Precursor (S5P), the first of the European Sentinel satellites dedicated to monitoring atmospheric composition, was launched. The mission objectives of S5P are to globally monitor air quality, climate and the ozone layer in the time period between 2017 and 2023. The single payload of the S5P mission is TROPospheric Monitoring Instrument (TROPOMI), a nadir viewing shortwave spectrometer that measures from UV to the near IR. The TROPOMI Aerosol Layer Height (ALH) product focuses on retrieval of vertically localized aerosol layers in the free troposphere (above ABL height which is usually 1 km), such as desert dust, biomass burning aerosol, or volcanic ash plumes. The height of such layers is retrieved for cloud-free conditions.

INOE (<https://environment.inoe.ro/>) was working with the [E-PROFILE ALC network](#) to validate the TROPOMI ALH product (Algorithm Theoretical Basis Document -[ATBD](#)) (Nemuc et al 2021) but also using EARLINET data (Nemuc et al, 2022). There are several differences in the sensing principles between active remote sensing of aerosols from ground-based stations and passive remote sensing of aerosols from satellites, both in the terms of retrieval/measurement method and in terms of vertical resolution.

Ground-based Lidar (Light detection and ranging) remote sensing techniques can provide accurate vertical profiles of the aerosol backscatter and extinction coefficients, which are representative of the aerosol load, with vertical resolution of a few meters. An algorithm based on the gradient method (Nicolae et al, 2018) was applied to the attenuated backscatter profiles to retrieve all aerosol layers including those in the free troposphere. A cloud mask algorithm was also applied to the measured profiles (e.g. Biniotoglou et al 2018). Nemuc, A. et al., 2022 presented few case studies of long range transported aerosols over Romania as seen by ground based lidar and TROPOMI, oral presentation at the Sentinel-5P Mission: 5 years anniversary meeting, physical meeting, October 11, 2022: <https://s5pcampaigns.aeronomie.be/ProjectDir/Outreach/NemucSessionAersolsClouds.pdf>.

Mihailidis et al. 2023 has published a study investigating the ability of TROPOMI to derive accurate geometrical features of lofted aerosol layers, selecting the Mediterranean Basin as the study area by comparisons with ground-based correlative measurements from lidar. The choice of the EARLINET stations close to the sea has been performed considering the limitation of the TROPOMI ALH algorithm over land surfaces in providing accurate retrievals. Using these sites presented an opportunity to study the effect of the surface albedo on the validation of ALH product performing separate analyses over land and sea. The results presented encourage the operational usage of that particular methodology approach in validation processes for satellite aerosol height products using lidar data from EARLINET.

4 EarthCare cal/val rehearsal campaign

EarthCARE, an ESA Earth Explorer Mission ready to be launched in May 2024, is designed to observe the atmosphere using advanced technology including high spectral resolution lidar, Doppler cloud radar, multi-spectral imager, and broadband radiometer. With these instruments, it functions as a space-based observatory for remote sensing of aerosols and clouds. It shares similarities with observatories within PROBE's networks.

During the preparatory measures for EarthCARE Mission Validation, a 2-Month Rehearsal Campaign In the framework of the ATMO ACCESS pilot activities for internal stakeholders has been initiated to support the validation: <https://www.actris.eu/EarthCARE%20Mission%20Validation>.

The aim of this campaign is to provide tailored products for cal/val of EUMETSAT satellite missions (aerosol & clouds) as follows:

Aerosol Parameters:

- Provide additional aerosol parameters, such as aerosol layer heights, for enhanced analysis and understanding of aerosol distribution and properties.

2. Cloud Parameters:

- Offer additional cloud parameters, like cloud fraction within the footprint, to provide more comprehensive information on cloud cover and characteristics.

3. **CLOUDNET Product Update:**
 - Update the content of the CLOUDNET product to include the latest data and analysis techniques, ensuring it remains relevant and useful for users.
4. **Timeliness and Data Access:**
 - Prioritize timeliness and easy access to data by implementing efficient data delivery mechanisms and user-friendly interfaces for accessing and downloading data.
5. **Quality and Standards:**
 - Maintain high-quality standards by adhering to established quality control procedures and ensuring that data meet Fundamental Remote Sensing Monitoring (FRM) standards.
6. **Reprocessing of Historical Data:**
 - Reprocess historical data using updated algorithms and methodologies to ensure consistency and accuracy across different time periods.

Activities to be implemented before for EarthCARE Launch:

1. **Preparation QA and QC**
 - Ensure thorough preparation for the launch of the EarthCARE mission, focusing on Quality Assurance (QA) and Quality Control (QC) processes to guarantee the reliability and accuracy of data collected.
2. **Near-Real-Time (NRT) Data Provision to ECVT:**
 - Establish a system for the near-real-time provision of data products to the Essential Climate Variables Team (ECVT), ensuring timely access to critical information for climate monitoring and analysis.
3. **Correlative Observations:**
 - Conduct correlative observations through simulated overpasses, aligning ground-based measurements with satellite overpasses to validate and enhance the accuracy of remote sensing data.
4. **Field Campaigns:**
 - Organize field campaigns beneath the orbit of EarthCARE, leveraging opportunities to collect complementary ground-based data that can provide context and validation for satellite observations.
5. **Transfer of Standards & Procedures:**
 - Facilitate the transfer of standards and procedures developed for EarthCARE to other scientific communities, such as the European Space Agency (ESA) and the Multi-angle Polarimetric Lidar (MPL) community, to promote consistency and interoperability across research efforts.

This scheme aims to address the various aspects of preparing for the launch of the EarthCARE mission, ensuring the provision of data to relevant teams, conducting correlative observations and field campaigns, and facilitating the transfer of standards and procedures to other scientific communities.

Other calibration/validation (cal/val) campaigns related to EarthCARE mission (<https://earth.esa.int/eogateway/news/an-overview-of-the-earthcare-mission>) uses most of the instruments from PROBE's network and a list could be found in this document: <https://az659834.vo.msecnd.net/eventsairwesteuprod/production-nikal-public/1c6ca5307f2044f8b2573a68e4a83e53>

5 Aeolus cal/val campaign

Aeolus (https://www.esa.int/Applications/Observing_the_Earth/FutureEO/Aeolus) was the first space mission to acquire profiles of the wind on a global scale. The mission employed a high-performance Doppler wind lidar-ALADIN -Atmospheric LASer Doppler INstrument, based on direct-detection interferometric techniques. ADM-Aeolus was launched on 22 August 2018 and ended in July 2023.

It contributed to aerosol observations through provision of atmospheric backscatter and extinction coefficient profiles at 355 nm, but there was no instrument capability to distinguish optically thin cloud and aerosol layers.

Prior to the satellite launch, the ESA promoted several campaigns for the intercomparison of the satellite's products, for both wind and optical retrievals (Straume et al., 2019), in order to determine possible observation biases and increase the data quality.

Statistical validation of Aeolus L2A particle backscatter coefficient retrievals over ACTRIS/EARLINET stations on the Iberian Peninsula was published in Abril-Gago et al. 2022 highlighting the importance of ground based networks for satellite validation.

ASKOS project (<https://askos.space.noa.gr/>) it was focused on the Cape Verde campaign design to assess the quality of the aerosol and cloud products of Aeolus satellite based on Intensive Operation measurements during summers of 2021 and 2022, using Aerosol, wind, radiation, polarization and cloud remote sensing, airborne & in-situ platforms, and UAV/balloon launches, instruments similar with the ones of PROBE's network.

The ASKOS measurements delivered essential data for the validation of Aeolus optical properties products in the tropics, with a particular focus on Saharan dust. It also provided important information to improve the characterisation and calibration of the satellite's ALADIN instrument, as well as for the quantitative validation of the Aeolus instrument and optical properties' data in terms of systematic and random errors (<https://earth.esa.int/eogateway/news/jatac-askos-the-campaign-validating-aeolus-data-from-the-ground>).

6. Other future satellite Mission that PROBE's networks will be useful

WIVERN & AEOLUS 2

The PROBE's ground-based network could be use in calibration validation of future missions as it is **WIVERN**: a Mission to Observe Global in-cloud Winds, Clouds and Precipitation as part of the ESA Earth Explorer 11 Programme to be launched 2031 (<https://wivern.polito.it/>) and also **Aeolus-2** (measuring unique profiles of Earth's winds from space) is included in the Earth Observation Proposal at ESA's upcoming Council at Ministerial Level (https://www.esa.int/ESA_Multimedia/Images/2022/10/Aeolus-2_Value_of_Information).

ABLE

Other future mission to be launched by NASA is A31M-2548 Atmospheric Boundary Layer Lidar Pathfinder (ABLE): Differential Absorption Lidar for Humidity Profiling, Aerosol/Cloud Profiling, and Planetary Boundary Layer Heights: <https://agu.confex.com/agu/fm23/meetingapp.cgi/Paper/1360114>.

7 Eumetsat

Combined radar/Lidar products are used for independent validation of cloud products from Imagers of EUMETSAT satellites. Validation OCA-Optimal Cloud Analysis vs. ACTRIS-Cloudnet using MTG-FCI data can be found on slide 8 of the following link <https://az659834.vo.msecnd.net/eventsairwesteuprod/production-nikal-public/2194d4a0c792415d8d58c6f56531e42a>.

FRM4AER project: Service for FRMs for Copernicus Aerosol Product Cal/Val Activities- a strategic project within the EUMESAT plan for calibration validation is looking into including the ground based lidar network into a operational database for Sentinel-3 OLCI Aerosol Layer Height (https://ceos.org/document_management/Working_Groups/WGClimate/Meetings/WGClimate%20GHG-TT-3/3b_Marbach_EUM_calval_supoort_strategy.pdf).

Few research areas of satellite community in which there is a need for further developing products characterising Atmospheric layers have been underlined (e.g. Sentinel-5P TROPOMI Aerosol Layer Height Product and Sentinel-3 OLCI Aerosol Layer Height).

8. IASI temperature and humidity profiles

Space-borne hyperspectral infrared (HSIR) sounders provide vertically resolved information of atmospheric temperature and humidity (in approximately 1 km layers), and of surface and cloud properties. EUMETSAT is operationally exploiting the IASI (Infrared Atmospheric Sounding Interferometer) mission, with three instruments flying in Low Earth Orbit (LEO) on-board the Metop-A, -B and -C satellites. Future hyperspectral missions are in preparation, with increased sounding and coverage performances to ensure service continuity beyond 2024. This includes the geostationary infrared sounder IRS on board Meteosat Third Generation (MTG), which will deliver operational atmospheric sounding at unprecedented spatial and temporal sampling (every 30 minutes over Europe), and the Next Generation IASI-NG, with improved vertical atmospheric information content. Satellite products performances are routinely monitored, notably against world-wide coordinated radiosounding *in situ* measurements. These are usually launched only once or twice a day, at fixed synoptic times and often a few hours apart from the satellite overpasses, making direct inter-comparisons difficult. Ground-based microwave radiometers (MWR) with temperature and humidity profiling capabilities can fill this gap, especially in the ABL.

Through networking initiated by PROBE partners (Météo-France, University of Cologne), EUMETSAT conducted (for the first time) an inter-comparison study, between operational IASI and MWR sounding products to evaluate

- the potential of an operational MWR network for the daily monitoring of satellite HSIR products, with the goal to initiate an automatic statistical analysis and reporting;

- the co-registration (temporal and spatial) uncertainties and how they contribute to the difference budget with radiosondes in the current performance monitoring;
- the ability to detect temperature inversions close to the ground by IASI, given its limited vertical resolution in the boundary layer.

To that end, MWR products from six different sites of the [SOFOG3D](#) international fog campaign (2019/2020) led by Météo-France have been statistically analysed and compared to IASI products, quantifying the satellite product accuracy in relation to different atmospheric conditions (cloudiness, boundary layer stability...). A first inter-comparison showed that IASI and MWR temperature profile correspond within +/- 1 K up to about ~4 km. Larger differences (~1 K) are seen near the surface and the lowest ABL. (Fig. 1) more especially when the scanning capability of MWRs is used to improve the vertical resolution of MWR products.

Figure 2: BIAS and STD between IASI and MWR temperature profile during the SOFOG3D campaign. Plot courtesy of Constanze Seibert, University of Hamburg and EUMETSAT

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